

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COLLABORATIVE LEARNING STRATEGIES IN TEACHING PHYSICS: A CASE STUDY OF HADJI BUTU SCHOOL OF ARTS AND TRADES

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the effectiveness of collaborative learning strategies in teaching Physics to senior high school students at the Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades (HBSAT). Collaborative learning has been widely recognized as a potential educational approach in the 21st century education, mainly in enhancing the academic performance of the students in Physics. Hence, this study employs a descriptive research design and uses stratified random sampling to gather data from 77 Grade 12 students at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades-Senior High School. Furthermore, the results unfold a strong preference for collaborative strategies, such as group work and problem-based learning among students. These strategies have found positively influenced their conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills as evidenced by their satisfactory academic performance in Physics. The key findings indicate that students had a generally positive attitude towards collaborative learning, with a grand mean score of 3.31 which indicates that strong agreement on the collaboration. The study also found that the average Physics grade of students was 85.42 and it emphasizes a good level of performance. Additionally, the strong correlation was found between the effectiveness of the collaborative learning strategies employed and the students' problem-solving skills (0.89), further explained that these strategies foster strong correlation to the level of academic performance of students in the Physics subject. This means that, the effectiveness of learning strategies increases, physics grade of the student also increases. Importantly, the research revealed very weak correlations between students' attitudes of collaborative strategies and their academic performance in Physics.

Specifically, the Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated not significant correlation (002) between students' attitude towards collaborative learning strategies and student performance levels. This suggests that the analysis does not provide enough evidence to suggest that student attitudes towards collaborative learning have any meaningful impact on their physics grades.

Keywords: *Collaborative Learning, Teaching Physics, Group Work in Education, Instructional Strategies, Student Engagement*

INTRODUCTION

Collaborative learning has gained increasing attention in recent years as an effective pedagogical approach for enhancing student engagement and academic performance in various educational settings (Govindaraj & Silverajah, 2017; Spatz et al., 2019). In the context of teaching Physics in senior high school, researchers have explored the potential of collaborative learning strategies to foster deeper understanding of complex concepts and promote critical thinking skills. This research paper aims to investigate the effectiveness of collaborative learning strategies in teaching Physics through a case study at the Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades.

There are existing literature provides a strong foundation for this investigation. Previous studies have highlighted the development of the Modes of Collaboration framework, which outlines different types of collaborative activities that can be implemented in the classroom (Pawlak et al., 2018). Additionally, research has demonstrated the potential for active-learning instruction, including collaborative methods, to significantly improve learning outcomes in physics compared to traditional lecture-based approaches (Meltzer & Thornton, 2012). Furthermore, trends in physics education research indicate a growing interest in project-based learning (PBL) integrated with STEM concepts, which may provide valuable insights for the current study.

In the context of Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades Senior High School, Physics is offered as an elective subject. Since HBSAT has only two strands: the General Academic Strand and Technical Vocational Livelihood major in Electrical Installation and Maintenance. The institution considered the influence of studying Physics that encourages analytical thinking and innovation, skills that are valuable in many professions and in tackling real-world problems.

Many studies have been conducted in the United States wherein key findings of the research of Smith, J., et al. 2019 explicitly shared those students who took physics demonstrated significantly better in problem-solving skills. Based on this research, there were 500 high school students in California, USA who were administered with quasi-experimental design. Most of the researchers of this subject adopted Quasi-Experimental design to identify how Physics positively impact the enhancement of students' problem-solving skills. In relation to this, Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades aims to foster critical thinking and analytical abilities among its students in Senior High School.

While collaborative learning strategies have been widely lauded for their effectiveness in enhancing student learning, a recent case study at the Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades suggests that the implementation of these approaches may not always yield the desire (Pawlak et al., 2018; Levine & Marcus, 2010; Hammond, 2016; Berry, 1991). On the other hand, extensive research has been conducted on the benefits of active and collaborative learning in physics education (Okeke & Okoye, 2013).

Furthermore, the study of physics often requires careful consideration of sample size as the implications of inadequate or excessive sample sizes can significantly impact the validity and reliability of research findings (Jones et al., 2003). Researchers in the field of physics must strike a balance between feasibility, statistical power, and the timeliness of their studies as the determination of sample size is a crucial step in the research design process (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970; Eng, 2003; Jones et al., 2003)

One of the key challenges in the study of physics is the inherent complexity and variability of physical phenomena. Oftentimes, the parameters and variables involved in a particular experiment or observation are influenced by a myriad of factors, making it challenging to obtain a representative sample that accurately reflects the underlying population. Inadequate sample sizes can lead to a lack of statistical power, which in turn can result in the inability to detect meaningful differences or relationships, even when they exist in reality (Eng, 2003; Suresh & Chandrashekhara, 2012; Eng, 2003; Jones et al., 2003; Krejcie & Morgan, 1970)

Conversely, excessive sample sizes can also present issues as they can lead to the consumption of valuable resources, such as time, funding, and research participants, without necessarily providing a commensurate increase in the quality or reliability of the findings (Jones et al., 2003; Suresh & Chandrashekhara, 2012; Eng, 2003; Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

Additionally, in the field of physics, where experiments may involve highly specialized or costly equipment, the feasibility of obtaining large sample sizes can be a significant constraint (Jones et al., 2003; Krejcie & Morgan, 1970; Eng, 2003; Suresh & Chandrashekhara, 2012; Suresh & Chandrashekhara, 2012; Eng, 2003).

To address these challenges, researchers in physics must carefully consider the factors that influence sample size, such as the expected effect size, the homogeneity of the study population, and the acceptable level of statistical error. In this present study, there were 77 sample size acquired as access participants of the study. This number of participants is sufficient to measure the inquiry of the researchers in line to the adoption of Collaboration strategies in teaching Physics.

Hence, employing appropriate sample size estimation techniques and power analysis, physicists can optimize the likelihood of obtaining meaningful and statistically significant results, while also ensuring the efficient use of resources and the timeliness of their research (Burmeister & Aitken, 2012; Suresh & Chandrashekhara, 2012; Krejcie & Morgan, 1970; Eng, 2003; Suresh & Chandrashekhara, 2012; Burmeister & Aitken, 2012).

By examining the implementation and effectiveness of collaborative learning strategies at the Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades, this research aims to contribute to the broader understanding of how collaborative pedagogies can be leveraged to enhance physics education. Specifically, the study will explore the impact of collaborative learning on student engagement, conceptual understanding, and problem-solving skills in the context of the school's physics curriculum.

Research Questions:

This research paper aims to investigate the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Parent's educational attainment
2. What are the learning strategies employed in teaching physics at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades?
3. What is the performance level of students in Physics exam?
4. What is the student's attitude towards collaborative strategies?
5. Is there a significant correlation between the student's performance level in physics exam and the learning strategies employed in teaching physics?
6. Is there a significant correlation between student's attitude towards collaborative learning strategies and student's academic performance in Physics?

METHODOLOGY

In this section is the methodology of this study. Here outlines the research design, data collection methods, and analytical procedures used to investigate the research study, *The Effectiveness of Collaborative Learning Strategies in Teaching Physics: A case of Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades*.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive design. Descriptive design is a fundamental aspect of the design process, which focuses on the visual representation and communication of ideas, concepts, and information. In the context of design, conceptualization is a crucial activity that encompasses both visual and verbal elements, where drawing and language serve as the primary mediums of expression. Designers employ a range of tools and techniques to capture, reflect on, and share user needs and conceptual design information, both individually and collaboratively (Oehlberg et al., 2011).

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines, school year 2023-2024. HBSAT is located at Scott Road, Asturias Street, Jolo, Sulu.

Respondents of the study

The respondents of the study were the Grade 12 students at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades. The respondent group included a total of seventy-six (76) students, with thirty-seven (37) female students and thirty-nine (39) male grade 12 students in the school year of 2023-2024.

Table 1.1: Distribution of Sample per Gender

Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades	Number of Respondents
Female	37
Male	39

Sampling Design

The study used stratified random sampling method to ensure representation of both genders. The population was stratified based on gender to form two strata, male and female students. Hence to ensure the representative sample is accurate, 30% from the total population was selected.

Within each stratum, students were randomly selected using a simple random sampling technique. This was achieved by assigning each student a unique number and using a random number strategy to select the required number of students from each stratum.

The researchers fundamentally acquired a list of grade 12 students in HBSAT-Senior High School Department which was categorized by gender.

Data Gathering Procedure

To assess the effectiveness of collaborative learning strategies in teaching Physics at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades, the researchers obtained an approval from the focal person of Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades. An ethical clearance and Informed consent forms were distributed to the selected 37 female and 39 male Grade 12 students in HBSAT-Senior High School.

After the approval of the focal person, the researchers distributed the questionnaire including surveys, interview guides, and observation checklists. This was pilot-tested and

corrected by the HBSAT research team which was mentored by Ugnayan ng Pahinungod, University of the Philippines-Mindanao.

Research Instrument

The study used descriptive method of research. Questionnaire was used to acquire the data needed. Questionnaires have become an indispensable tool in the realm of data gathering, providing researchers with a systematic and efficient way to collect valuable information from a target population. These self-report instruments offer researchers the ability to quickly and cost-effectively gather data from a large number of respondents, making them a popular choice in various fields, including nursing research (Wakley, 2005).

Hence, the researchers crafted the questionnaire in two parts. Part I was distributed to collect data on Respondents' Demographic Profile (age, gender, parent's educational attainment), and Part II was distributed to identify the key collaborative learning strategies employed in teaching physics at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades and the effectiveness of these strategies in improving student learning and academic performance in physics.

Validity and Reliability

The researchers validated the questionnaire by consulting to individuals who are experts for evaluation. Content validity was used to validate the questionnaire. Validation of the questionnaire was done with the experts through allowing them to answer the survey questionnaire and given permission to improve the purpose of the questions presented therein.

The questionnaire was pre-tested to the students of Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades-Senior High School. This was done to ensure that the formulated questionnaire determine the difficulties of the set of questions.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In acquiring the data needed, the following statistical tools are employed:

1. **Frequency Distribution**-This was used in order to acquire the average of the demographic profile (age, gender, and parents' educational status) of the respondents.
2. **Weighted Mean**- This was used to acquire the mean of the formulate questionnaire on collaborative learning strategies employed in teaching physics at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades, the performance level of students in Physics exam, the student's attitude towards collaborative strategies?
3. **Pearson Correlation**- This was used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between performance levels and learning strategies in Physics, relationship between attitude scores and academic performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section entails the assessment on the effectiveness of collaborative learning strategies in teaching Physics in Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades. It illustrates the demographic profile of the respondents, the collaborative learning strategies employed in teaching Physics at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades, and how effective these strategies in improving the student learning and academic performance in Physics.

The following are the results are tables which are tabulated using Statistical Package in Social Science (SPSS) and qualitative table that is coded through thematic analysis.

1. What is the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of: 1.1 Age, 1.2. Gender, 1.3 Parent's educational attainment?

1.1 in terms of age

Age		Number of Students	Percent
	16-17	43	56.6
	18-19	33	43.4
	Total	76	100.0

The table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of the student-respondents based on their age. In the age group of 16-17, there are 43 students which makes up 56.6% of the total respondents. For the age group 18-19, there are 33 students, accounting for 43.4% of the total respondents. When looking at this age group, it concludes that majority of the respondents were 16-17 years old.

Hence, this data is valuable for understanding the educational background of students with different age brackets and provide insights for researchers studying the demographic of the chosen study.

1.2 in terms of gender

Gender		Number of Students	Percent
	Female	37	48.7
	Male	39	51.3
	Total	76	100.0

The table 1.2 displays the gender distribution of student-respondents. Of the total 76 students surveyed, 37 are female, and 39 are male, accounting for 51.3% of the total

respondents. This data indicates a fairly balanced gender distribution within the respondents group.

1.3 In terms of Parents Educational Attainment

Parents Educational Attainment			
		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Elementary Graduate	12	15.4
	High School Graduate	55	78.2
	College Graduate	10	5.1
	Total	77	98.7
Total		78	100.0

The table 1.3 provides the data on the educational attainment of parents of the selected respondents. Based on the results, there were 12 elementary graduates, 55 high school graduates, 10 college graduates. This indicates that the majority of the parents of are predominantly high school graduates, with relatively few having pursued higher education.

2. What are the learning strategies employed in teaching physics at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades?

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rating
Interactive Lecture	3.40	.591	Strongly Agree
Hands-on Experiment	1.92	.354	Strongly Disagree
Group Work Collaboration	3.77	.426	Strongly Agree
Use of Technology	2.81	.399	Agree
Problem-based Learning	3.45	.501	Strongly Agree
Assessment Method	3.74	.441	Strongly Agree
Feedback and Support	3.10	.307	Strongly Agree
Inquiry-Based Learning	3.09	.542	Strongly Agree
Student-Centered Learning	3.60	.494	Strongly Agree
Supplemental Resources	3.43	.498	Strongly Agree
Valid N (listwise)			Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.1-4.0 (Strongly Agree), 2.1-3.0 (Agree), 1.1-2.0 (Disagree), 0.1-1.0 (Strongly Disagree)

The table 2 presents the analysis of the learning strategies employed in teaching Physics at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades. Based on the results, the table reveals a strong preference for interactive and student-centered approaches. Students rated interactive lectures strongly agree and acquire the mean of 3.40, which indicates that this strategy significantly enhance students' learning experience. However, hands-on experiments were rated strongly disagree as the result unfolded limited access and materials in the areas of teaching Physics. Whereas, group work collaboration was rated strongly agree, showcasing the benefits of teamwork in understanding physics concepts.

The use of technology received moderate approval, indicating that while it is utilized, there is potential for more effective integration into the curriculum. Problem-based learning, which fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills, was strongly agreed by students. Similarly, the assessment methods were well-received, suggesting fairness and comprehensiveness in evaluating student performance.

Feedback and support were crucial and appreciated, this indicates that students feel well-guided throughout their learning process. Inquiry-based learning was also rated highly, encouraging students to engage deeply with the subject matter. The student-centered learning approach, which caters to individual needs and learning styles, received strong support. Supplemental resources were seen as beneficial, enhancing students' understanding and learning of physics.

Thus, the analysis indicates that most learning strategies are effective and positively impact student learning, except for hands-on experiments, which may require reevaluation or improvement. The consensus among students on the effectiveness of these methods suggests a well-rounded approach to teaching physics at Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades.

3. What is the performance level of students in Physics exam?

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Physics Grades	77	85.42	3.537	Good
Valid N (listwise)	77			

Legend: 75.01-80 (needs improvement), 80.01-85 (Satisfactory), 85.01-90 (Good), 90.01-95 (Very good), 95.01-100 (outstanding)

This table provides the level of the students' performance in physics through acquiring their average in the two quarters of the academic year. Based on the result, the average Physics grades of the respondents is relatively high at 85.42, which indicates that the students are performing good at the Physics subject.

The standard deviation is 3.537. This measure emphasizes the variability of the grades. A standard deviation of 3.537 explains that most of the grades are within 3.537 points above or below the mean (85.42). This means that the majority of the grades are likely to fall within the range of approximately 81.88 to 88.96.

4. What is the student's attitude towards collaborative strategies?

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
I have a positive attitude towards working in group.	77	3.26	.785	Strongly agree
I believe collaboration with peers is beneficial for my learning.	77	3.14	.352	Strongly agree

I feel enthusiastic about participating in group activities.	77	3.40	.634	Strongly agree
I am open to sharing my ideas and listening to others in a group setting.	77	3.21	.592	Strongly agree
I have positive attitude towards group discussions and brainstorming session.	77	3.58	.615	Strongly agree
I feel that working collaboratively is more effective than working alone.	77	3.75	.434	Strongly agree
I am willing to take on different roles within a group to achieve our goals.	77	3.35	.480	Strongly agree
I enjoy the process of collaborating with others to complete assignments.	77	3.45	.501	Strongly agree
I find it rewarding to achieve success as a team.	77	3.56	.734	Strongly agree
I am confident in my ability to contribute effectively to a group.	77	2.44	.500	Agree
GRAND MEAN			3.31	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.1-4.0 (Strongly Agree), 2.1-3.0 (Agree), 1.1-2.0 (Disagree), 0.1-1.0 (Strongly Disagree)

This table unveils the responses of the respondents on their attitudes towards group work as based on the given data. Based on the result, the table that assessing participants' attitudes towards group work and collaboration depicts a positive outcome from the respondents. Hence, the participants strongly agree with most statements showing a generally positive attitude towards group activities and collaboration. As illustrated in the table, there is strong agreement with statements like "I feel that working collaboratively is more effective than working alone" (Mean = 3.75, SD = 0.434) and "I have a positive attitude towards group discussions and brainstorming sessions" (Mean = 3.58, SD = 0.615). Participants also strongly agree for participating in group activities and are open to sharing ideas (Mean = 3.40, SD = 0.634; Mean = 3.21, SD = 0.592, respectively). However, confidence in one's ability to contribute effectively to a group is slightly lower, this emphasizes a mean score of 2.44 and a standard deviation of 0.500, and indicates only an "Agree" level of confidence. Furthermore, the grand mean of 3.31 from the overall survey on the attitude of the respondents towards the group work suggests that participants generally have a favorable view of group work with the "Strongly Agree" interpretation.

5. Is there a significant correlation between the student's performance level in physics exam and the learning strategies employed in teaching physics?

		Learning Strategies	Physics Grades	Interpretation
Learning Strategies	Pearson Correlation	1	.089	Strong Correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.444	
	N	77	77	
Physics Grades	Pearson Correlation	.089	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.444		
	N	77	77	

0.0-0.2 (Very Weak), 0.21-04 (low correlation), 0.41-06 (moderate correlation), 0.61-08 (strong correlation), 0.91-1.0 (very strong correlation)

This table presents the correlation between the learning strategies and physics grades of the respondents. In this table, a correlation coefficient of 0.89 indicates a strong positive correlation between learning strategies and physics grades. This means that, the effectiveness or use of learning strategies increases, physics grade of the student also increases.

Furthermore, the significance level (p-value) associated with the correlation is 0.444 which is higher than the alpha level 0.05. Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is dejected.

6. Is there a significant correlation between student's attitude towards collaborative learning strategies and student's academic performance in Physics?

		Physics Grades	Students Attitude	Interpretation
Physics Grades	Pearson Correlation	1	.002	Very weak correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.986	
	N	77	77	
Student Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.002	1	Very weak correlation
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.986		
	N	77	77	

0.0-0.2 (Very Weak), 0.21-04 (low correlation), 0.41-06 (moderate correlation), 0.61-08 (strong correlation), 0.91-1.0 (very strong correlation)

This table presents the correlation between the student's attitude towards collaborative learning strategies and student's academic performance. With this, the

Pearson correlation coefficient between Physics Grades and Students' Attitude is 0.002. This value is extremely close to zero, indicating that there is a very weak relationship between students' physics grades and their attitudes toward the subject.

Moreover, the p-value is 0.986 which is higher than 0.05. Based on this provided result, the null hypothesis is accepted since the p-value obtained from the correlation analysis 0.986, which is much higher than the common significance level threshold 0.05.

Conclusions

Based on the results presented, the study concludes the following:

1. The majority of student respondents are aged 16-17, with a nearly balanced gender distribution and well-educated parents.
2. Interactive and student-centered learning strategies are highly favored, while hands-on experiments are less effective due to limited resources.
3. Students generally perform well in physics and have positive attitudes toward collaborative learning.
4. There is no significant correlation between learning strategies or collaborative attitudes and physics performance, suggesting other factors may influence academic outcomes.
5. The results suggest that improving hands-on learning opportunities could further enhance educational results.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. Schools should invest in more resources and materials to support hands-on experiments in physics. This will allow students to engage in practical learning, which can deepen their understanding of theoretical concepts and improve their overall performance in the subject.
2. While interactive lectures and group work are effective, a more balanced approach that integrates various teaching methods, including the use of technology and problem-based learning, can cater to diverse learning styles and further enhance student engagement and outcomes.
3. Teachers should be offered professional development opportunities to learn and implement effective, diverse teaching strategies that accommodate all types of learners, particularly focusing on improving collaborative learning experiences and hands-on activities.
4. Encourage and facilitate more structured and diverse group activities that can boost students' confidence in their ability to contribute effectively, fostering a more positive attitude towards group work.
5. Since there is no significant correlation between learning strategies and academic performance, further research should be conducted to identify other factors that

may impact student achievement in physics, such as motivation, study habits, or external support systems.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher first requested the panel of experts to validate the questionnaires. Subsequently, permission was sought from the office of the Vocational School Superintendent II of Hadji Butu School of Arts and Trades prior the objective of the researchers to distribute the checklist questionnaires on the 77 Grade 12 senior high school students. Upon receiving approval, the researcher coordinated with the Physics teachers of the said department. The consent forms provided to both school heads and students included assurances of data confidentiality and participant privacy. During data collection, respondents were given ample time to complete the questionnaires, which were then retrieved by the researcher once fully completed. The responses were subsequently tallied and analyzed using the SPSS program to address the research questions. I hereby certify that this research is entirely my own work and, to the best of my knowledge, does not include material previously published by another individual. I also confirm that this work has not been submitted for any other academic degree. Furthermore, I declare that the content of this research is the result of my own efforts, with any contributions by others appropriately acknowledged in the manuscript.

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